

Table 1. Leaf Bl severity at different rice crop stages. Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986.

Observation	Disease severity (%)							
	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8
	<i>Wet season</i>							
45 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10		
60 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5	8-10	15-20	25-30
75 DAS	0-0.05	1	2-3	5	8-10	15	20	30
	<i>Dry season</i>							
45 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10	15	
60 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10	15	20-25
75 DAS	0-0.05	1	2	3	5-8	10	15	20-30

Table 2. Relationship between leaf Bl severity and yield loss (\hat{y}), derived from pooled data of two seasons. Pathum Thani Rice Research Center, Thailand, 1986.

Predictor variable ^a	Regression function	F ^b	R ²
BLA 45 DAS	$\hat{y} = 31.18 + 18.54 \ln(x)$	121.2***	0.92
BLA 60 DAS	$\hat{y} = 9.38 + 2.99x$	116.3***	0.89
BLA 75 DAS	$\hat{y} = 0.06 + 3.08x$	355.1***	0.96

^aBLA 45 DAS = % leaf area infected at 45 days after sowing. ^b*** P < 0.001.

severity during the reproductive stage (75 DAS) was most closely related to yield loss. Based on the third function,

1% infected leaf area corresponds to 3% yield loss. □

Estimating yield loss to rice blast (Bl) disease

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Rice yield loss equivalents for leaf and neck Bl found in earlier experiments had to be derived from multiple regression functions, because of mixed infection by several diseases. We conducted a field experiment to study the effect on yield of Bl alone.

RD23 was direct sown 20 Aug 1986 at Pathum Thani Rice Research Center. A source of inoculum was provided near the experimental plot. Ten 0.5-m² plots were staked out in an area 800 m². Incidence and severity of rice Bl was observed two times, at maximum tillering (60 d after sowing [DAS]) and 1 wk before harvest. Data were collected on percentage leaf area infected, number of tillers, number of panicles, number of

Linear regression between leaf Bl percentage and percent yield loss at Pathum Thani Research Center, 1986 wet season.

panicles with neck Bl, filled grain weight, and empty grain weight.

Sample plots showed 0-70% infected leaf area. Neck Bl incidence was 11-35%. Leaf Bl severity was not correlated with neck Bl incidence ($r = 0.233$ ns).

Yield of the plot free of leaf or neck Bl symptoms was used to calculate percentage yield loss in the other plots. Linear regression analysis resulted in a model to predict percentage yield loss from leaf Bl severity (see figure). The regression accounts for 78% of the variability in yield loss. □

Reaction of four rice cultivars to grassy stunt virus (GSV) strain 2 under natural conditions

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During wet season 1988 (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov), a severe outbreak of GSV in parts of Kuttanad, Kerala, caused severe damage to the rice crop. Serological tests at Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, confirmed that the outbreak was caused by GSV strain 2. We evaluated MO 5, MO 6, KAU153-1, and KAU93 for resistance to this strain under three levels of fertilizer, in a split-plot design with three replications. Disease incidence was scored just before panicle initiation.

MO 5, MO 6, and KAU153-1 were moderately susceptible; KAU93 was susceptible (see table). □

Resistance of rice varieties to GSV strain 2. Kerala, India, 1988 wet season.

Cultivar	Parentage	GSV damage (0-9)
MO 5	IR11-1-66/Kochuvithu	5
MO 6	IR8/Karivennel	5
KAU153-1	IR1561/Ptb 33	4
KAU93	Jaya/Ptb 33	7

Control of blast (Bl) in main field and nursery with some new fungicides

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Bl causes considerable yield losses in Nellore District under favorable weather conditions from Oct to Feb. We tested seven EC/WP and four granular fungicides to control leaf and neck Bl in transplanted rice in wet seasons (Oct-Feb) 1985-86, using highly susceptible IR50.

Plots were laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Fertilizers, 180-60-30 kg NPK/ha, were applied, phosphorus and potash as basal and N in three splits: 1/3 basal, 1/3 at tillering, 1/3 at panicle initiation. Plant spacing was 15 × 15 cm.

EC/ WP fungicides were sprayed at tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering. Granular fungicides were applied 30 kg/ha when initial Bl symptoms appeared during tillering and 40 kg/ha during flowering. Leaf and neck Bl were measured 10 d after last application from five 1-m² random samples.

All the EC/WP fungicides but Natural Plant Product-1 effectively reduced leaf Bl (see table). Neck Bl was not reduced.

Granular fungicides chlobenthiazole 5 G and pyroquilon 5 G effectively controlled leaf Bl. Neck Bl incidence was not reflected in yield. Plots that showed

Influence of new EC/WP and granular fungicides on incidence of Bl and yield of IR50. Nellore, India. 1985-86.

Fungicide	Concentration	Leaf Bl (%)	Neck Bl (%)	Grain yield (kg/plot)
<i>EC/WP fungicides</i>				
Carbendazim 50 WP	1 g/liter	2.2	24.3	1.6
Edifenphos 50 EC	1 ml/liter	1.9	16.4	2.2
Pyroquilon 50 WP	1 g/liter	1.7	26.3	1.9
Isoprothiolane 40 EC	1 ml/liter	1.4	17.1	1.8
IBP 48 EC	1 ml/liter	2.0	20.1	1.7
Natural Plant Product – 1	2.5 ml/liter	36.3	26.5	0.9
Thiophanate methyl 70 WP	1 g/liter	2.2	23.3	1.3
Untreated check		32.9	30.8	0.8
LSD (0.05)		18.6	ns	0.6
<i>Granular fungicides</i>				
Chlobenthiazole 6 G	70 kg/ha	2.0	32.2	2.4
Pyroquilon 5 G	70 kg/ha	0.7	20.4	3.0
IBP 17 G	70 kglha	39.4	17.2	1.5
Probenazole 8 G	70 kg/ha	46.7	21.6	0.9
Untreated check		81.5	10.3	0.5
LSD (0.05)		33.1	11.4	1.0

more leaf Bl infection had few panicles with neck Bl, perhaps because panicles

on severely leaf Bl-affected plants only partially emerged. □

Insect management

Effect of lunar phase on attraction of rice pests to black light trap

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We collected rice insect pests in a Krishi Prakash Black Light Trap (KPBL-T) during six lunar cycles.

Three days on either side of the date of a full moon was taken as a full moon

week. Three days on either side of a new moon was taken as a new moon week. In-between periods formed the last and first quarter moon week. From total insect catches, ratios were obtained to compare full moon week catches with new moon week catches.

Moonlight had a significant effect on nocturnal activity of stem borer (SB), leafhopper (LF), brown planthopper (BPH), and green leafhopper (GLH). Full moon and new moon week ratios were 1:1.1, 1:1.2, 1:2.2, and 1:2.3, respectively (see table). This indicates that nocturnal activity of SB and LF is much less influenced by moonlight than that of BPH and GLH. □

Severe outbreak of rice gall midge (GM) in the savannah zone, Nigeria

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The savannah zone of Nigeria, stretching latitudinally across the southern midsection, with its river floodplains and inland valley swamps, is an important rice-growing area. Production probably accounts for more than 70% of Nigeria's total. Varieties grown include FARO 12 (Mas), FARO 13 (IR8), FARO 15, FARO 16, FARO 18 (Tjina or China), FARO 26 (TOs 78), FARO 29 (BG90-2), and IR5.

A severe outbreak of GM (*Orseolia oryzivora* H & G.) damaged crops sown Jul-Aug 1988 (wet season). Earlier (Jun-Jul) crops had little damage.

The Abakaliki locality in Anambra State (8° 10' E, 6° 20' N) had the most severe damage. Incidence of silvershoots was high (45-80% of all tillers). Yields in

Effect of lunar cycle on the black light trap catches of some rice pests. Madurai, India.

Insect	Insects ^a (no.)				Ratio of full moon week to new moon week
	Full moon week	Last quarter week	New moon week	First quarter week	
Yellow SB <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	291.04 (1.94)	264.81 (1.89)	332.95 (2.30)	194.69 (1.98)	1:1.1
LF <i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	169.73 (1.55)	176.88 (1.90)	202.25 (2.19)	63.76 (1.50)	1:1.2
BPH <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	159.80 (2.00)	157.14 (2.09)	376.11 (2.47)	128.45 (1.92)	1:2.4
GLH <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.	193.53 (1.82)	146.86 (2.10)	455.43 (2.64)	175.58 (2.09)	1:2.3

^a Mean of six lunar cycles. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.